

Criteria

Please answer the questions below to determine your eligibility in this survey:

Are you at least 18 years old?

Yes

No

Are you currently working/studying OR have worked/studied software development?

Yes

No

Do you have 3+ years of work experience OR a post-secondary degree/diploma, in a field OTHER than software development?

Yes

No

Consent Form

Information Letter and Consent Form

Title of Project: Towards Understanding Perceptions and Barriers of Having Non-Traditional Academic Backgrounds in Software Engineering.

Purpose of Research: This study is conducted by Dr. Mei Nagappan at the Cheriton School of Computer Science at University of Waterloo, Canada. The objective of this study is to understand if and how experiences in non-software field(s) affect one's experiences when switching into, and staying in, the software field.

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria: We seek participants (18 and older) who have experience (a post-secondary degree/diploma or 3+ years of work experience) in a field other than software development, and who

- currently work as a software developer, OR
- are currently studying software development, OR
- previously worked in or studied software development, AFTER their experience in another field

Study details: If you decide to participate, you will be completing a survey that will take approximately 20 minutes. This survey will include questions about your demographics (e.g., gender, age) and your experiences in both software and non-software fields.

Remuneration: You will receive a remuneration gift card of CAD\$10 for completing this survey.

Withdrawal: Participation in this study is voluntary. You may decline to answer any question in the questionnaire, and you can withdraw your participation in the study by not submitting the survey form. You cannot withdraw from the study after the form has been submitted.

Benefits: There is no direct benefit to participants from this study.

Risks: There are no known or anticipated risks from participating in this study.

Videotaping, Audiotaping and Screen Captures: You will not be videotaped, audiotaped or screen captured while completing the survey.

Confidentiality: Your identity will be confidential. All of the data will be summarized and no individual will be identifiable from these summarized results. Anonymous quotations from your open text responses may be used in papers and publications resulting from this study. The data, with no personal identifiers, collected from this study will be maintained on a password-protected computer database in a restricted access area of the university and external servers. Paper forms will be stored in a locked cabinet at Davis Center, University of Waterloo. The data will be electronically

archived after completion of the study and maintained for a minimum of 7 years and then erased. The data collected for this study will be kept at the University of Waterloo. Only researchers and external collaborators associated with the study will have access to the data. The data will not be shared publicly. Your contact information (e.g., email) will be stored separately from your survey data and will be deleted as soon as the data collection and remuneration period has ended. When information is transmitted over internet privacy cannot be guaranteed. There is always a risk that your responses may be intercepted by a third party (e.g., government agencies, hackers). University of Waterloo practices are to turn off functions that collect machine identifiers such as IP addresses. The host of the system collecting the data, such as Google Forms, may collect this information without our knowledge and make this accessible to us. We will not use or save this information without your consent. **Questions:** Should you have any questions about the study, or if you would like to receive a copy of the results of this study, please contact Dr. Mei Nagappan (mei.nagappan@uwaterloo.ca).

This study has been reviewed and received ethics clearance through a University of Waterloo Research Ethics Board (ORE #43447). If you have questions for the Board, contact the Chief Ethics Officer, Office of Research Ethics, at 1-519-888-4567 ext. 36005 or ore-ceo@uwaterloo.ca.

Consent for Participation: By signing below, I consent to my participation in this study designed to understand the perceptions and barriers faced by those in software engineering with non-traditional academic backgrounds. I have read the letter of information and understand the risks and benefits of participation. I also understand that:

- My identity will be kept confidential.
- I am free to withdraw from the study at any time before submitting the form without reason or consequence.
- I have been told the purpose of the experiment and am free to ask questions at any time.

- I consent and want to participate.
- I do not consent and do not want to participate.

Demographic and Background

What is your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- Non-conforming
- Non-binary
- Prefer to self-disclose
- Prefer not to say

What is your age?

- 18-25
- 26-30
- 31-35
- 36-40
- 41-45
- 46-50
- 51-55
- 56-60
- 61-65
- Over 65

What is/are your nationality/nationalities?

What is/are your native language(s)?

A native language is defined by the [Cambridge Dictionary](#) as "the first language that

you learn".

How would you best describe yourself? (Select more than one, if applicable)

- White or Caucasian
- Black or African-American
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Latino or Hispanic
- Asian
- Pacific Islander or Hawaiian
- Middle Eastern or North African
- Indigenous
- Prefer not to say
- Other

Switching into Software Development

What field(s) is/was your non-software experience in?

Why did you decide to switch into software development ?

Work Experience

Are you currently working as a software developer?

- Yes, full-time
- Yes, part-time
- No, but I have worked as a software developer in the past
- No, I have never worked as a software developer

How long have you worked or have you been working with software development?

- Less than 3 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16-20 years
- More than 20 years

What is/are your software-related work experience(s)? Please select all software-related job(s) below that you have worked before.

- Automation engineer - software
- Backend engineer
- Cloud architect/engineer
- Application architect/engineer
- DevOps engineer
- Embedded software engineer
- Mobile applications developer
- Quality assurance engineer
- Back-end web developer
- Front-end web developer
- Full-stack web developer
- Game developer
- Software developer/engineer
- Artificial intelligence programmer
- Graphics programmer
- Other:

Educational Background

Click to write the question textWhat is your formal educational background? Please list your post-secondary degree(s)/diploma(s) with their titles (e.g., Bachelor's) and their status (completed, uncompleted, or in progress) in chronological order, or put 'no degree/diploma' otherwise.

What were the ways you have learned software development? (Select more than one, if applicable)

- Bootcamp
- Self-study
- High school
- Elective courses in university/college
- Required courses in university/college
- Other:

Are you currently studying software development in a post-secondary degree/diploma program?

- Yes, full-time
- Yes, part-time
- No, but I did in the past
- No, I have never formally studied software development

Barriers and Mitigation Strat 1

	Not applicable	Not relevant at all	A little relevant	Moderately relevant	Very relevant	Extremely relevant
Work responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>					
Financial cost related to resources for job search	<input type="radio"/>					
Difficulty competing/keeping up with colleagues even after getting a development job	<input type="radio"/>					
Difficulties finding a job	<input type="radio"/>					
Uncertainty planning an educational pathway	<input type="radio"/>					
Financial cost of software engineering education	<input type="radio"/>					
Uncertainty due to conflicting opinions	<input type="radio"/>					
Lack of professional networking opportunities	<input type="radio"/>					
Lack of self-confidence	<input type="radio"/>					

Please list below any barriers that were relevant in your experience but are not in the list above.

Barriers and Mitigation Strat 2

Please list below other mitigation strategies that are/were effective to mitigate the relevant barriers.

How do you believe your educational/occupational background that is not in software development affected the barriers you faced when switching into software development?

- Significantly worse
- Moderately worse
- No effect
- Moderately better
- Significantly better

In what ways, if any, is/was your educational/occupational background that is not in software development advantageous to you while switching into, or in, your software development career?